

Is Sustainable Food Choice Related to Our Empathy? The Role of Empathy in Organic Food Consumption

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Previous research has shown that cognitive empathy is positively associated with environment concerns, while affective empathy is negatively associated with environmental problems. This study aims to investigate the role of empathy in sustainable food choice. A total of 102 participants (61 women) made 10 discrete choices between organic and conventional food products in a virtual supermarket. Affective and cognitive empathy was measured using the questionnaire of cognitive and affective empathy (QCAE). Multiple logistic regressions revealed that cognitive empathy predicted the likelihood of organic fruit and vegetables being selected, though the relationships were inverse. Higher cognitive empathy scores were associated with a decreased likelihood of organic food being chosen. Conversely, there was a null effect of affective empathy on food choices. These findings demonstrated that empathy for nature and other livings can be suppressed when making sustainable food choices. It can be otherwise concluded that consumers make sustainable decisions based on their sense of social responsibility.

Keywords: Sustainability; Empathy; Organic food; Discrete choice experiment

As sustainability has become an integral aspect of our lives, organisations have begun to implement ecolabelling schemes. Ecolabelling is an effective communication vehicle through which to attach the concept of green marketing, such as the use of the “bio” label, to reassure the consumer of the quality and safety of a product (Lewandowska et al. 2018; Ottman 2011). Organic foods are those which have been naturally produced, without genetic modification, synthetic fertilisers or pesticides, and are free of antibiotics and growth hormones (Dahm, Samonte and Show 2009).

Consumer preference for organic food differs depending on each individual's motivation, attitude, cultural influences, and psychological construct (Gil, Barr and Ford 2005; Grunert et al 2014; Thøgersen 2010). One relevant psychological construct, the influence of which has yet to be examined on sustainable consumption, is empathy. Thus, the current study seeks to investigate the effects of empathy, with an emphasis on the affective and cognitive components on consumers' organic food preferences.

At present, a limited number of studies have sought to address the role of empathy in ecological behaviours (Sevillano, Aragonée and Schultz 2007; Schultz 2002; Tam 2013). Empathy is a psychological construct in which individuals' observations, memories, knowledge and reasoning yield insights into the thoughts and feelings of others (Ickes 1997, 18). The two most frequently researched constructs of the multidimensional structure of empathy are affective empathy and cognitive empathy. While the former relates to the recognition and understanding of another's emotional state, the latter characterises the understanding of another's mental state, such as their beliefs and intentions (Blair 2005; Flavell 1999). Early work conducted by Schultz (2002) demonstrated that concern for environmental issues is associated with the degree to which individuals view themselves as being a part of nature. In his study, participants viewed pictures of humans engaged in recreational activities in nature, animals in nature, and animals that had been harmed by polluted nature. Participants were then asked to rate perspective-taking and environmental concern questions on a 5-point scale. The results showed that participants' perspective-taking scores were significantly higher when viewing images of animals being harmed by an environment that had been polluted. Additionally, higher scores in perspective-taking were associated with higher levels of environmental concern. In line with these findings, a subsequent study

conducted by Sevillano et al. (2007) succeeded in replicating Schultz's (2002) results, while also determining that a higher level of personal distress (i.e., subscale of affective empathy) was associated with lower levels of environmental concern. These findings clearly demonstrated that viewing animals that had been harmed by polluted nature involved cognitive empathy. However, individuals are unable to affectively empathise with the environment when their personal distress concerns are elevated. This can be explained by the parallel nature of empathy, in which individuals prioritise concern for themselves over concern for other living beings. As a result, some individuals are able to empathise with other human beings personally, but demonstrate less concern for environmental problems that affect other living things.

Thus far, the studies conducted by Schultz (2000) and Sevillano et al. (2007) have shed light on the role empathy plays in environment concern. However, no studies have attempted to describe the influence of empathy on sustainable consumption. Therefore, the goal of the current study is to investigate the effects of empathy on consumers' food choices. We hypothesised that individuals with high levels of cognitive or affective empathy would be more likely to choose organic food products. Further, we expected to see the effects of empathy on consumers' preference for animal-based products, such as dairy (milk, cheese).

Methods

Participants

One hundred and twenty-one participants were recruited via the Neurons' Inc subject pool and a Facebook post. Twenty participants were excluded as they did not

meet the sampling criteria (e.g., above the age limit, vegan diet), and to mitigate noisy data. The remaining participants' data (61 women and 41 men, mean age 29.89 years; range 18-53 years) was used for the analysis. Participants were required to fast for four hours prior participation in the study to ensure they were neither hungry nor full during the experiment. It was not possible to include participants with special dietary restrictions (e.g., vegan) due to the nature of the experiment. Each participant was awarded two hundred DKK [Danish Kroner] for contributing to the experiment. Informed consent was obtained prior to data collection.

Experimental Procedure

Discrete-choice experiment in the virtual supermarket

A discrete-choice experiment was conducted within a virtual-reality based supermarket. To familiarise participants with the environment, prior to the experiment commencing, they practiced standard virtual moves, including picking-up and placing items into the shopping trolley, and inspecting the grocery list, within a neutral setting.

Each participant was provided a grocery list containing ten food items and briefed that they were entering a hypothetical scenario in which they had to mimic their real shopping behaviour. Hypothetical scenarios in virtual reality are comparatively useful in studying decision-making, as they can enhance the sense of presence within a given situation, when compared with their written counterpart. This allows for a more realistic representation of real-world decision-making (Van Gelder et al. 2019).

Participants made ten discrete organic versus conventional product choices based on the grocery list provided. Three product categories were selected for the

virtual shopping task – fruits and vegetables, dairy, and chocolate and wine. The full list of the products is as follows: apple, banana, cucumber, broccoli, tomato, cheese, milk, wine, milk chocolate, and dark chocolate. Many of these products were selected as they represent the most popular organic items in Denmark (Sennov 2016). Upon completion of the virtual shopping task, participants were asked to populate a survey containing basic demographic questions and a questionnaire of cognitive and affective empathy (QCAE). The order of the questionnaire and virtual shopping task was counterbalanced.

Questionnaire of Cognitive and Affective Empathy (QCAE)

The QCAE aims to measure individuals' cognitive and affective empathy (Reniers et al. 2011). It comprises thirty-one items, each of which is answered on a 4-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = strongly agree). Affective empathy explores the ability of the respondent to experience another's emotional state, while the cognitive empathy explores the respondent's capacity to understand another's situation. The affective construct contains four subscales, including Emotion Contagion (four items), Proximal Responsivity (four items) and Peripheral Responsivity (four items). An example of one of the subscales is "friends talk to me about their problems as they say I am very understanding". The cognitive construct contains two subscales, including Perspective Taking (ten items) and Online Simulation (nine items). An example of a subscale item is "I find it easy to put myself in somebody else's shoes". The affective empathy score is the sum of all four subscales, while the cognitive empathy score is the sum of the two subscales, respectively. The QCAE achieved a good internal consistency, with Cronbach's α ranging from .65 to .85 (Reniers et al. 2011).

Statistical Analyses

The statistical analysis was performed using R (Version 1.2.5033), with the dichotomous outcome variable, food choices, being coded 0,1 (Not organic/Organic). The predictor variables were the emotional and cognitive empathy scores. To determine the effect empathy has on food choices, logistic regressions were required, as these are able to extend linear regressions to noncontinuous outcomes using logit link functions and estimate the probabilities between two classes. As previous research has posited, organic food choices have a high level of heterogeneity, the following variables were selected as covariates: gender (Grunert, Hieke, and Wills 2014), income (Moser and Kleinhüchelkott 2018), age (Vecchio and Annunziata 2015), education (Lockie et al. 2002), and employment (Lockie et al. 2002). To answer the established question, multiple logistic regressions on fruits, vegetables, and dairy products were computed. Each item within the food category was then combined into an overall choice from the category. To proffer an example, to determine the combined fruit selection required the combination of choices in both the apple and banana category. A total of ten multiple logistic regressions were computed.

Results

Characteristics of the Sample

Table 1 sets out the socio-demographics of the 102 participants. There was a higher number of female samples (59.8%) than male. Most of the participants were aged between 25 and 34 (51.9%) and highly educated, with 50% of the participants holding a university degree. Although more than half of the participants fell into the low-income

group (69.9%), consumption frequency of organic food was relatively common, as it was determined that at least 52.9% of participants regularly purchased organic food, with a further 13.7% of participants stating that they almost always purchased organic food.

Choice Behaviour in Fruit Category

Multiple logistic regressions were conducted to ascertain the effects of cognitive and affective empathy on participants' preference for organic fruits, while controlling for age, gender, education, employment, and income. Table 2 presents the results of three of the models: banana, apple and combined fruits (unstandardised logistic coefficients with odds ratios). The combined fruit choices were calculated by summing the selections of both organic and conventional apples and bananas. The first step was to establish the association between empathy and food choices within the fruits category. Contrary to expectations, neither cognitive ($p = 0.61$) nor affective empathy ($p = 0.17$) were significant predictors of combined choices of fruits. This implies that none of the empathy constructs can predict food choices in either the apple or banana category. Furthermore, it was discovered that when examining individual fruit items, cognitive empathy can be a predictor of organic food choice in banana ($b = -0.13$, $p = 0.00$). Although this was significant when all other variables remained constant, the odds ratio was less than 1 (.88 in the banana model), which indicates that each unit increase in the cognitive empathy score is associated with a 12% decrease in the odds of an organic banana being selected. The percentage change in the odds of food choice having a value of 1 was calculated by subtracting 1 from the ratio and multiplying the

value by 100. The multiple logistic models employed accounted for approximately 22% (McFadden R Squared) of the variance in food choice of banana amongst consumers.

Choice Behaviour in Vegetables Category

Three multiple logistic regressions were performed to examine the effects of cognitive and affective empathy on the likelihood of participants selecting organic vegetables (while controlling for age, gender, education, employment, and income). Table 3 presents the results from four different models: tomato, broccoli, cucumber and combined vegetables (unstandardised logistic coefficients with odds ratios). Contrary to the hypothesis, the combined vegetables model demonstrated that neither cognitive empathy ($p = 0.99$) nor affective empathy ($p = 0.70$) were significant predictors of food choice in all vegetables. Upon closer examination of each vegetable product, cognitive empathy was found to be a significant predictor of cucumber ($b = -0.10$, $p = 0.01$). However, similar to the findings relating to the previous banana selection, an odds ratio below 1 was recorded (.90 in the cucumber model). Thus, the odds of an individual selecting organic food compared to a conventional cucumber increased by a factor of .90 for a unit of decrease in the cognitive empathy score. To clarify, the odds of choosing an organic cucumber decreased by 10% for each unit increase within the cognitive empathy score. The logistic model employed accounted for 11% of the variance (McFadden R Squared) in relation to the food choice of cucumber amongst consumers.

Choice Behaviour in the Vegetables Category

Three multiple logistic regressions were performed to assess whether cognitive

and/or affective empathy could predict dairy food choices, including milk and cheese, or combined choices of the two, while controlling for age, gender, education, employment, and income. As indicated in Table 4, the results showed that the overall model for milk, cheese, and combined choices of dairy were not statistically significant ($p > .05$). The results therefore contradicted the hypothesis that individuals' empathy influences their food choices in relation to animal-based products.

Discussion

The experiment sought to identify the role empathy plays in organic food preferences across multiple categories. Contrary to the hypotheses, the results demonstrated a null effect of affective empathy on organic food choices in the fruits, vegetables, and dairy categories. Significantly, neither cognitive nor affective empathy influenced consumer decision-making towards animal-based products. Contrarily, while cognitive empathy predicted preferences for organic banana and organic cucumber, the relationships were consistently inverse within these two products, indicating that consumers chose conventional banana and cucumber more frequently when their level of cognitive empathy was lower. The data also revealed significant heterogeneity of cognitive empathy for different food products, insofar as choosing organic fresh goods – but not organic dairy products – could be predicted by cognitive empathy.

From a theoretical perspective, the heterogeneity of cognitive empathy reflected in different food items can be explained by a recently proposed model known as the heterogeneity model of empathy (Light 2019). The author argued that empathic responses do not always require an act of helpfulness, and that individuals can demonstrate empathy without feeling or expressing it consciously. That being said,

consumers only need be reflective of their choices, without having to empathise with living things associated with the products. However, the model only supports empathy between humans, and has yet to be extended or applied to other living creatures. Consistent with Sevillano et al. (2007), a null effect of affective empathy on pro-environmental behaviour was discovered. A speculative account proposed by Tam (2013) argued that for some individuals, the boundary between humans and nature is blurred, while others consider themselves to be part of nature. A psychological factor that must be considered in the context of this study is that some consumers, rather than empathising with other livings and nature, may simply feel responsible for purchasing ecolabelling products. This phenomenon is known as consumer responsibility for sustainable consumption (CRSC) (Luchs et al. 2015). An example of CRSC is the emotional guilt which can predict up to 46% of the sustainable purchase intention (Antonetti and Maklan 2014).

A few limitations of the current study should be addressed. While the results are based on a large sample size, the sample population was focused on individuals aged between 25 and 34, which could potentially limit the generalisability towards older groups. Further, price was not included within the study parameters, thus it was not incentive compatible. As economists have frequently argued, incentive compatible responses in studies are “real responses”, such that participants’ decisions in the task are related to real outcomes (Harrison 2006). Future VR-oriented studies may wish to consider incentivising consumer shopping behaviour to enhance the validity of results.

To conclude, the current study provides evidence of the role empathy plays in organic food preference, with the findings suggesting that individuals need not empathise with the source of the food product they select (i.e., plants, animals) to make

organic food choices. It is plausible that consumers empathise with the environment without translating this to their consumer behaviour. Sustainable decisions may be predicated on a sense of responsibility towards sustainable consumption. From a public policy perspective, empathising with the environment may promote conservation behaviours, though the effectiveness will depend on each individual's understanding of nature, as well as the engagement between ecolabelling and consumers.

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Table 1. Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Sample ($n = 102$), Distribution in Percentages.

Description	Percentage (%)
Gender	
Male	40.2
Female	59.8
Age	
18-24	25.4
25-34	51.9
35+	22.5%
Income	
Low	69.6
Medium	25.5
High	4.9
Education	
High school	8.8
Vocational training	5.9
Bachelor's degree	50.0
Master's degree or above	35.3
Diet	
Omnivore	96.1
Vegetarian	2.0
Others	2.0
Organic food consumption frequency	
Never	14.7
Rarely	32.4
Often	52.9
Nearly always	13.7

Note: Income low: monthly income is under 25,000 DKK, medium: monthly income is between 25,000 and 60,000 DKK, high: monthly income is over 60,000 DKK per month.

Table 2. Summary of logistic regression analyses for variables predicting decisions to choose organic food for fruits category ($n = 102$), controlling for demographic variables

Predicto	Banana			Apple			Fruits (Combined)		
	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>
(Intercep	15.39			1.31			3.35		
CE	-0.13	0.87	0.79 –	-0.08	0.92	0.85 –	-0.02	0.98	0.91 –
AE	-0.09	0.91	0.80 –	0.07	1.07	0.94 –	-0.07	0.92	0.82 –
McFadd		0.22			0.08			0.09	

Note: CE = Cognitive Empathy. AE = Affective Empathy. Covariates are age, gender, education, employment, and income (omitted from the table). OR = Odds Ratio. Organic food as a predictor was coded as 1 for organic and 0 for non-organic (conventional). Female is the reference category for gender. Full-time is the reference category for employment. Income and education had extremely uneven numbers between groups and therefore was coded as a numeric variable.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Table 3. Summary of Logistic Regression Analyses for Variables Predicting Decisions to Choose Organic Food for Vegetables Category ($n = 102$), Controlling for Demographic Variables

Predict	Tomato			Broccoli			Cucumber			Vegetables		
	<i>B</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>
(Interc	2.48			5.14			7.82			1.07		
CE	-0.02	0.97	0.90 –	-0.05	0.94	0.88 –	-0.10	0.90	0.82 –	0.00	1.00	0.93 –
AE	0.00	1.00	0.88 –	-0.04	0.95	0.84 –	0.03	1.04	0.91 –	-0.02	0.98	0.87 –
McFadd		0.10			0.07			0.11			0.03	

Note: CE = Cognitive empathy. AE = Affective empathy. Covariates are age, gender, education, employment, and income (omitted from the table). OR = Odds Ratio. Organic food

as a predictor was coded as 1 for organic and 0 for non-organic (conventional). Female is the reference category for gender. Full-time is the reference category for employment. Income and education had extremely uneven numbers between groups and therefore was coded as a numeric variable.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Table 4. Summary of Logistic Regression Analyses for Variables Predicting Decisions to Choose Organic Food for Dairy Category ($n = 102$), Controlling for Demographic Variables

	Milk			Cheese			Dairy (Combined)		
Predict	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI</i>
(Interc	-0.71			2.18			4.69		
CE	-0.04	0.96	0.87 –	0.02	1.03	0.95 –	0.04	1.05	0.97 –
AE	0.10	1.11	0.96 –	-0.09	0.91	0.80 –	-0.09	0.91	0.79 –
McFadd		0.14			0.09			0.12	

Note: CE = Cognitive empathy. AE = Affective empathy. Covariates are age, gender, education, employment, and income (omitted from the table). OR = Odds Ratio. Organic food as a predictor was coded as 1 for organic and 0 for non-organic (conventional). Female is the reference category for gender. Full-time is the reference category for employment. Income and education had extremely uneven numbers between groups and therefore was coded as a numeric variable.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.